

Online Shopping in India: A Cross-Cultural Study of Paradigm Shift in Tier II Cities

Prof. (Dr.) Faize Ali Shah

Director, Eshan College of Management, Farah, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India

Vanshika Tandon

Assistant Professor, Uttam Institute of Management Studies, Agra, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract:

Online merchandizing environment has become fiercely competitive aiming for profoundly understanding consumers' persona that fascinates them to shop online. The current study has been construed to comprehend this. First, differential role of consumer demographics in creating awareness and affecting online shopping on cross-cultural design is scrutinized. Then, relationships between consumer satisfaction and factors affecting consumer buying behaviour have been explored. After conducting KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, bivariate analysis has examined the effect of

factors affecting online shopping on consumer behaviour of 400 respondents belonging to four urbanized cities of India, through t-test and one way ANOVA. Subsequently, the impact of factors affecting consumer buying behaviour on consumer satisfaction has been investigated by linear regression analysis. Findings suggest age affects online consumer awareness with no differential role of consumer demographics in the effect of factors affecting online shopping cross-culturally. Next part highlights two factors- family influence (motivational factor) and trend (perceptual factor) establishing strong relationships with online consumer satisfaction. This study aids marketing managers and researchers to scrutinize how age affects present-day online consumer awareness. The non-effective differential role of online consumer demographics on a cross-cultural design can aid in marketing strategy formulation for investigating novel relationships between factors affecting consumer satisfaction. It is striking that age affects present-day online consumer awareness without any differential role of consumer demographics, cross-culturally. Moreover, the impact of family influence and trend on consumer satisfaction is leading towards transformational consumer buying behaviour patterns needing recognition which is the researchers' contribution to extant literature.

Keywords: *Online shopping, consumer buying behaviour, bivariate analysis, consumer satisfaction, step-wise regression analysis.*

Introduction

Online Shopping- An Overview

Internet is the most domineering technological revolution (Fu et al., 2020) of the twentieth century. The cybernetic system comprehends

communicating, collaborating, merchandizing, investments and buying (Puspita & Rohedi, 2021). Online shopping entails purchasing commodities or amenities over the Internet (Sunitha & Gnanadhas, 2014) being correlated to buying behaviour (Bagga & Bhatt, 2013).

Waheed & Yang (2018) posit online shopping behavior of consumers is reliant on a multiplicity of dynamics allied to each other. It comprises online users entrusting their buying intentions and instructions (Aragoncillo & Orus, 2018) with subjective and banking details to facilitate payments (Pandey et al., 2019); including the implementation of trade and commerce (Valaei & Nikhashemi, 2017) as well as shipping (Salehi, 2012) and delivery of goods (Das & Ghose, 2019). The webspace is ever-expanding and transformative thereby this has become a source of interest for the researcher to scrutinize consumer behaviour influenced by impact of persistent merchandizing tactics.

Awareness for Online Buying

Shopping on the web unswervingly (Adam & Hussain, 2017) depends on how aware the consumers are regarding this arena (Chen et al., 2013). Importance of consumer awareness in marketing depends on need (Pícha & Navrátil, 2019) which is recognized through buying behaviour (Sangroya & Nayak, 2017). As the virtual marketplace is mounting (Carroll & Wagar, 2010), buyers are becoming aware of the features, pros and cons of items desired by them (Ahmed et al., 2017). Innumerable choices, deals (Senecal & Nantel, 2004) and services (Du et al., 2020) associated with the products have compelled shoppers to explore the cybernetic system. Notably, Quan et al. (2020) add the extent to which prospects become devoted buyers is staunchly related to awareness regarding the concept of online shopping towards specific online souks (Liu et al., 2017). Evidently, inherent facets of awareness have been contemplated in the present study.

Consumer Demographics Affecting Online Shopping

Role of the external environment during online shopping and decision making is evidently dependent on the demographic profile of consumers (Singh & Verma, 2017). It defines consumer purchase intentions depending on trust (Mehrotra et al., 2019). Adding to this, Aziz et al. (2014) specify that consumer ethnocentric tendencies are also affected by demographic set-up which might deepen the roots of

acculturation to a determinate extent (Carpenter et al., 2013). Yet cross-cultural consumer demographics have not been thoroughly investigated pertaining to online marketplace (Bhat et al., 2021). The researchers attempt to contribute in extant literature for a deepened understanding of drivers affecting online consumer buying behaviour specifically prevalent among consumers belonging to culturally varied tier-II cities.

Role of Consumer Satisfaction

The popularization of the concept of online buying (Tandon et al., 2018) has signified consumer satisfaction to become a key determinant (Jung & Seock, 2017) yet limited studies have investigated it effectively (Fargnoli et al., 2018) in terms of consumer psychographics. Any number of factors, including vendor or service characteristics (Sadeghi & Heidarzadeh, 2010) can impact intention of online shopping and decision making which may influence mindfulness levels (Raza et al., 2015). The significance of assessment of factors and its impact on satisfactory levels lies in its ability to fulfil users' requirements for escapism, inclination, aesthetic amusement, and/or emotional release (McQuail, 1983). The present study caters to identification of factors pertaining to attitude, perception and motivation for a profounder understanding of consumer satisfaction.

Objectives

An effective scrutiny requires fundamental objectives which direct (Ashman, 2009) the purpose and outline the foundation for conducting research. Initially, the researchers have studied the differential role of consumer demographics in creating awareness of online shopping among Indian consumers cross-culturally and found factors affecting online shopping in India to eventually assess the effect of such factors on their online buying patterns. Ultimately, the impact of online shopping on consumer satisfaction has been analysed.

Theoretical Framework

In order to penetratingly explore the inclination of consumers who get aware and encouraged towards procuring goods and services (Roth & Bösener, 2015) on web-based systems, review of past studies is binding. Many eminent scholars have contributed in scrutinizing the contemporary as well as impending aspects of online shopping behaviour which become a vital part of the lives of consumers, aiding in framing the proposed hypotheses.

Awareness Level Among Shoppers

For many buyers, shopping online has become a regular part of their lives (Liao & Chu, 2013), whereas others might have less knowledge about it (Makrides et al., 2019). What they require is technological upgradation and familiarity (Kimenju et al., 2005). Further, societal influences, media coverage and psychographic materialisms affect demands of specification. Zhao et al. (2016) enunciate stress-free shopping, ease of usage, elasticity and variety provoke awareness among online buyers. Moreover, Kavitha (2015) adds that a purchaser is aware of a new product or service offered online depending upon his/her cultural dimensions and societal norms (Bucko et al., 2018). Once aware, shoppers attempt for price sensitive information which influences buying decisions (Desai et al., 2021). Evidently, awareness forms an imperative part of buying behaviour which influences shopping patterns. Yet there is a dearth in existing literature signifying awareness level on cross-cultural design. The researchers aim to investigate in this context due to which the subsequent hypothesis has been framed.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the awareness level of online shopping among Indian consumers.

Identifying Differential Role of Consumer Demographics

Buying over the internet is dependent on mixt factors (Sahney et al., 2013) reliant on consumer adoption and usage (Chong et al., 2010), online marketing effectiveness (Kiang et al., 2000), subjective norms and cultural area (Xu, 2015). Yet, Kim & Kim (2004) scrutinize demographic

configurations being palpable enough to influence buyer choices (Singh & Rana, 2018). Though there is a vast expanse of demographic variables, gender affects individuals' proportion of necessities (Hasan, 2010) which is distinguished between 'forego' and 'must-buy'. What males consider to be absolute prerequisites might not induce females to buy at all (Hernández & Jiménez, 2011) requiring detailed analysis.

Difference between fulfilment and receptiveness among online buyers can also be due to their marital status (Sivakumar & Gunasekaran, 2017). An individual's requirements might initiate change (Nguyen & Homolka, 2021), from being self-centric to fulfilment of all-encompassing desires. Likewise, advantage for the attainment of optimal online service level is also provocative of educational dimension (Lennon et al., 2007). Focus on the aspects of a product, brand names (Park & Lennon, 2009), quality and availability of new goods and services (Khare & Rakesh, 2011) essentially correlates with educative patterns of shoppers belonging to diverse occupational backgrounds (Gehrt et al., 2012).

With technological advancements of the 21st century, generation gaps have also developed (Yang et al., 2019) making the youth exceedingly aware of the technical areas and novel developments (Anesbury et al., 2015). Furthermore, ability to reduce resistance to change by using technology (Kim et al., 2012) during online shopping might be affective of age-prone mentality (Shahbaz et al., 2019) which would impact the tendency of buyers to spend owing to their ubiquitous household incomes. Though precise work has been done in the context of consumer demographics, extant literature lacks in identifying differential role of the most effective demographic factor in creating awareness. Consequently, the researcher has opted to scrutinize the revolutionization of online buying based on gender, marital status, educational and occupational status, age and monthly household income.

Determining the Effect of Factors Affecting Online Shopping

Concurrence with the effect of demographic factors affecting online shopping clarifies online buyer behaviour (Manickam, 2009). As per Jsk (2017), what shoppers prefer to purchase is inherent element of their demographic profile. How frequent shoppers use cyberspace for need satiation depends on their gender (Thamizhvanan & Xavier, 2013) and age (Lissitsa, & Kol, 2016) considering perceived risks and security (Makhitha & Ngoben, 2021). However, Srinivasan et al. (2015) defend that family and peers is a causative factor but marital status is unrelated to buying choices. What consumers consider relevant depends on demographics but we found a lack of consensus among authors in two respects. First, a lone dominant demographic factor affecting online shopping and second, cross-cultural differentiation in effect of such factors. This needs to be assessed recurrently for a precise perspective on favourable buying intentions (Nampoothiri & Pravitha, 2021).

Factors Affecting Consumer Satisfaction

There is a multiplicity of factors affecting online consumer satisfaction (Latha & Suneetha, 2021) compelling us to construe further. Rao et al. (2021) mention that consumer perception and experience directly affected e-satisfaction during the unfortunate pandemic thereby impacting current buying behaviour. So, satisfaction is necessary but might not always be a sufficient condition leading towards e-loyalty and trust (Fang et al., 2016). Contradictorily, Nuryakin et al. (2016) suggest transaction convenience, access convenience and information convenience influence shoppers to inculcate satisfaction and trust. Adding further, Ludin et al. (2014) enunciate that e-loyalty, creation of valuable information quality and apt service capabilities maintain vigorous relationships. But Vasic et al. (2019) oppose that satisfaction is affective of information availability and shipping apart from secure networking concerns among buyers. To obtain clarity in determining the most influential factor affecting online purchase, the

undermentioned hypotheses had been constituted.

H₀₃: There is no significant impact of factors affecting online shopping on consumer satisfaction.

Methodology

Before beginning the survey, questionnaire was developed. First, the instrument design to measure the construct (Hair et al., 2009) was opted by the researcher. Further, it was sent to five marketing experts for scrutiny and rated items were eliminated accordingly. A pilot study was conducted on 30 respondents belonging to the city of Gurugram. Questions were reframed leading to a pilot study on 100 respondents and the reliability and validity of questionnaire were checked. All the items on the questionnaire have been taken on 5-point Likert scale. Here, Awareness represents (1= strongly disagree and 5= strongly agree), Attitude (1= strongly disagree and 5= strongly agree), Perception (1= strongly disagree and 5= strongly agree), Motivation (1= never and 5= always) and Customer Satisfaction (1= highly dissatisfied and 5= highly satisfied). The Cronbach's alpha for awareness, attitude, perception, motivation and consumer satisfaction was 0.861, 0.846, 0.824 and 0.8100 respectively. Overall, the scale showed acceptable reliability. For this study, data was collected from 400 respondents (Godden, 2004) residing in four culturally diverse cities of India i.e., Gurugram, Surat, Nashik and Madurai. Judgemental sampling was opted for selection of cities because these cities are technologically advanced whereas the selection of respondents was based on convenience.

In order to achieve the first objective, the first hypothesis was sub-categorized city wise and then each sub-hypothesis was again checked demographic factor wise. These hypotheses were analysed through t-test and one way ANOVA. The one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) is utilized for determination of any statistically significant differences between the means of two or more independent (unrelated) groups. It is capable to inform that at least two groups might be dissimilar.

Before scrutinizing the second hypothesis, data was subjected to Exploratory Factor Analysis through Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy. This is a test that indicates that how suited a particular data is for Factor analysis. It is a measure that varies between 0 and 1 where values closer to 1 are better. This test is followed by Bartlett's Test of Sphericity which tests the null hypothesis and states the presence of correlation matrix as an identity matrix. Both tests provide a minimum standard of passing before a factor analysis or a principal component analysis is conducted and provide some items that are highly loaded.

Furthermore, the main hypothesis was categorized city wise in order to again check each city wise hypothesis through demographic factors by using t-test and one way ANOVA. This aided in identifying whether the effect of the factors significantly affects the consumer or not.

For investigation of the impact of factors affecting on customer satisfaction, regression

analysis (Baiocchi, et al., 2010) has been opted which is linear modelling of relationships. The variable that is to be predicted is named as dependent variable or the outcome variable. On the other hand, the variable that is used to predict the other variable's value is known as independent variable or the predictor variable.

Analysis of Awareness Level

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the awareness level of online shopping among Indian consumers.

In order to investigate the differences in the awareness level of online shopping among Indian consumers, along with pre-defined hypothesis, classification of the respondents was done based on certain demographic factors comprising gender, marital status, educational status, occupational status, age and monthly household income.

H_{01.1} There is no significant difference in the awareness level of online shopping among Gurugram consumers.

Table 1. Awareness Level Based on Demographic Factors of Gurugram and Results of t-Test

Demographic Factors	t-test			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	T	Sig.
Gender	0.44	0.506	0.325	0.534
Marital status	0.575	0.501	0.462	0.645
	One Way ANOVA			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		ANOVA	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	F	Sig.
Educational Status	2.101	0.130	0.595	0.550
Occupational Status	0.560	0.572	0.110	0.884
Age	1.162	0.310	1.365	0.270
Monthly Household Income	3.121	0.640	0.351	0.643

Source: Primary Data

Note: t-test and f-test are significant at the 0.05 level

The t-test indicated that there is no significant difference in the gender wise awareness level of online shopping ($t = 0.325$, $p = 0.534$). Furthermore, no significant difference in the marital status wise awareness level of online shopping was observed ($t = 0.462$, $p = 0.645$).

As evident there was no significant difference in the educational status wise awareness level ($f = 0.595$, $p = 0.550$). Interestingly, there is no significant difference in the occupational status wise awareness level among the consumers due to any variants ($f = 0.110$, $p = 0.884$). Likewise,

no significant difference was noted in the age wise awareness level ($f = 1.365$, $p = 0.270$). Monthly household income wise awareness level also resulted in a similar manner ($f = 0.351$, $p = 0.643$).

$H_{01.2}$: There is no significant difference in the awareness level of online shopping among Surat consumers.

Table 2. Awareness Level Based on Demographic Factors of Surat and Results of t-Test

Demographic Factors	t-test			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	T	Sig.
Gender	0.301	0.850	0.241	0.802
Marital status	1.101	0.310	0.365	0.545
	One Way ANOVA			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		ANOVA	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	F	Sig.
Educational Status	1.424	0.248	0.604	0.533
Occupational Status	2.872	0.703	2.145	0.061
Age	1.362	0.171	2.344	0.034
Monthly Household Income	2.334	0.710	2.245	0.140

Source: Primary Data

Note: t-test and f-test are significant at the 0.05 level

The t-test results on gender and marital status clearly indicated that there is no significant difference in both gender wise awareness level ($t = 0.241$, $p = 0.802$) and marital status wise awareness level ($t = 0.365$, $p = 0.545$) of online shopping among consumers. No significant difference in educational status wise awareness level of the respondents was observed ($f = 0.604$, $p = 0.533$). There was no significant difference in the occupational status wise awareness level ($f = 2.145$, $p = 0.061$).

However, there is significant difference in the age wise awareness level of these respondents ($f = 2.344$, $p = 0.034$). There is no significant difference in the monthly household income wise awareness level ($f = 2.245$, $p = 0.140$). So, it can be stated that apart from the respondent's age, no other demographic factor affects the awareness level of online consumers.

$H_{01.3}$: There is no significant difference in the awareness level of online shopping among Nashik consumers.

Table 3. Awareness Level Based on Demographic Factors of Nashik and Results of t-Test

Demographic Factors	t-test			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	T	Sig.
Gender	0.289	0.788	0.342	0.783
Marital status	0.672	0.510	0.453	0.634
	One Way ANOVA			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		ANOVA	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	F	Sig.
Educational Status	2.011	0.134	0.593	0.532
Occupational Status	1.560	0.584	0.119	0.983
Age	1.154	0.322	1.298	0.265
Monthly Household Income	3.011	0.650	0.310	0.628

Source: Primary Data

Note: t-test and f-test are significant at the 0.05 level

There was no significant difference in the gender wise awareness level ($t = 0.342, p = 0.783$), correspondingly, there was not any significant difference in the marital status wise awareness level ($t = 0.453, 0.634$). The awareness level of both educational status ($f = 0.593, p = 0.532$) and occupational status ($f = 0.119, p = 0.983$) had no significant difference. Likewise, there

was no effect of age ($f = 1.298, p = 0.265$) and monthly household income ($f = 0.310, p = 0.628$) on the awareness level of the respondents.

$H_{01.4}$ There is no significant difference in the awareness level of online shopping among Madurai consumers.

Table 4. Awareness Level Based on Demographic Factors of Madurai and Results of t-Test

Demographic Factors	t-test			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	T	Sig.
Gender	0.313	0.810	0.245	0.808
Marital status	1.031	0.354	0.345	0.542
	One Way ANOVA			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		ANOVA	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	F	Sig.
Educational Status	1.495	0.264	0.598	0.531
Occupational Status	2.101	0.804	2.322	0.054
Age	1.302	0.161	2.254	0.032
Monthly Household Income	2.24	0.734	2.159	0.143

Source: Primary Data

Note: t-test and f-test are significant at the 0.05 level

After testing gender with the help of t-test, it resulted that gender wise awareness level was not impacted by any valuable significant difference ($t = 0.245, p = 0.808$). The marital status ($t = 0.345, p = 0.542$) gave identical results. Testing through one-way ANOVA revealed that there was no significant difference in educational status wise awareness level ($f = 0.598, p = 0.531$). The interpretations of occupational status were no different ($f = 2.322, p = 0.054$). Also, there is significant difference in the age wise ($f = 2.254, p = 0.032$) awareness level is noteworthy. But monthly household income does not affect awareness level ($f = 2.159, p = 0.143$).

Altogether, among all demographic factors except for age of the online buyers, there is no statistically reliable difference in the awareness level of online shopping among Indian consumers.

Analysis of Effect of Factors Affecting Online Shopping

H_{02} : There is no significant difference in the effect of factors affecting online shopping.

Table 5. KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

Factor	KMO	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		
		Approx. chi-square	df	Sig
Attitude	0.828	1437.669	55	.000
Perception	0.740	1310.190	28	.000
Motivation	0.769	1441.470	45	.000
Satisfaction	0.706	1665.546	55	.000

Source: Primary Data

Note: KMO, Kaiser-Meyer Olkin

In case of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy, the value of 0.6 (Kaiser, 1974) is suggested minimum but in the case of attitude, perception, motivation and customer satisfaction we get 0.828, 0.740, 0.769 and 0.706 respectively. All of them are very good. As evident through Bartlett's test of sphericity, all

the null hypotheses are rejected. Hence, it fulfils the minimum criteria to apply factor analysis.

H_{02.2}: There is no significant difference in the effect of factors affecting online shopping among Gurugram consumers.

Table 6. Effects of Factors Affecting Gurugram Consumers Based on Demographic Factors and Results of t-Test

Demographic Factors	t-test			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	T	Sig.
Gender	0.223	0.638	0.138	0.711
Marital status	0.382	0.538	1.469	0.228
	One Way ANOVA			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		ANOVA	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	F	Sig.
Educational Status	0.310	0.818	1.293	0.258
Occupational Status	0.107	0.956	0.286	0.594
Age	1.441	0.236	1.270	0.262
Monthly Household Income	0.586	0.626	1.784	0.185

Source: Primary Data

Note: t-test and f-test are significant at the 0.05 level

There is no significant difference in the effect of factors affecting online shopping among Gurugram consumers both gender wise ($t = 0.138$, $p = 0.711$) and marital status wise ($t = 1.469$, $p = 0.228$). The effect of both educational status ($f = 1.293$, $p = 0.258$) and occupational status ($f = 0.286$, $p = 0.594$) was found to be insignificant. The results of the effect of factor affecting online shopping age wise ($f = 1.270$, p

$= 0.262$) also gave similar results thereby failing to reject the hypothesis. Ultimately, monthly household income ($f = 1.784$, $p = 0.185$) gave no significant results.

H_{02.2}: There is no significant difference in the effect of factors affecting online shopping among Surat consumers.

Table 7. Effects of Factors Affecting Surat Consumers Based on Demographic Factors and Results of t-Test

Demographic Factors	t-test			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	T	Sig.
Gender	0.744	0.529	1.278	0.280
Marital status	1.602	0.194	1.437	0.218
	One Way ANOVA			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		ANOVA	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	F	Sig.
Educational Status	0.603	0.615	0.675	0.643

Occupational Status	0.643	0.589	0.640	0.670
Age	0.351	0.789	0.548	0.739
Monthly Household Income	1.742	0.184	1.164	0.337

Source: Primary Data

Note: t-test and f-test are significant at the 0.05 level

Gender ($t = 1.278$, $p = 0.280$) did not significantly affect online shopping and marital status was also found insignificant ($f = 1.437$, $p = 0.218$). When the other four factors were tested, educational status ($f = 0.675$, $p = 0.643$) also justified the proposed hypothesis and occupational status of the respondents ($f = 0.640$, $p = 0.670$) also did not affect the online shopping tendency. Interestingly, age ($f = 0.548$,

$p = 0.739$) strongly supported the hypothesis and ultimately, monthly household income ($f = 1.164$, $p = 0.337$) also stood in favour of the hypothesis, thereby failing to reject it.

$H_{02.3}$: There is no significant difference in the effect of factors affecting online shopping among Nashik consumers.

Table 8. Effects of Factors Affecting Nashik Consumers Based on Demographic Factors and Results of t-Test

Demographic Factors	t-test			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	T	Sig.
Gender	0.290	0.833	0.164	0.920
Marital status	1.080	0.381	0.768	0.514
	One Way ANOVA			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		ANOVA	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	F	Sig.
Educational Status	0.900	0.444	0.237	0.870
Occupational Status	1.234	0.302	1.134	0.339
Age	0.233	0.638	0.855	0.467
Monthly Household Income	1.248	0.288	1.323	0.272

Source: Primary Data

Note: t-test and f-test are significant at the 0.05 level

Both the gender ($t = 0.164$, $p = 0.920$) and marital status ($t = 0.768$, $p = 0.514$) failed to affect online shopping thereby the hypotheses were failed to reject respectively, though the difference in the numerical values is noticeable. The relationship between the effect of factor affecting online shopping educational status wise ($f = 0.237$, $p = 0.870$) was negative. Identically, the hypothesis associated with occupational status ($f = 1.134$, $p = 0.339$) was also failed to

reject being above the acceptable limits. It was found that age did not significantly develop ($f = 0.855$, $p = 0.467$) significant relationship with online shopping. Parallel results were obtained by testing monthly household income ($f = 1.323$, $p = 0.272$).

$H_{02.4}$: There is no significant difference in the effect of factors affecting online shopping among Madurai consumers.

Table 9. Effects of Factors Affecting Madurai Consumers Based on Demographic Factors and Results of t-Test

Demographic Factors	t-test			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	T	Sig.
Gender	0.382	0.338	0.058	0.810
Marital status	0.586	0.626	0.048	0.828
	One Way ANOVA			
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		ANOVA	
	Levene Statistics	Sig.	F	Sig.
Educational Status	0.744	0.529	0.028	0.868
Occupational Status	1.602	0.194	0.857	0.357
Age	0.603	0.615	0.619	0.433
Monthly Household Income	0.643	0.589	0.501	0.481

Source: Primary Data

Note: t-test and f-test are significant at the 0.05 level

The t-test involving gender undoubtedly supported the proposed hypothesis thereby failing to reject it by a minimal margin ($t = 0.058$, $p = 0.810$). Results obtained pertaining to marital status were identical ($t = 0.048$, $p = 0.828$). Though the value of $f = 0.028$ of educational status was found to be low, ($p = 0.868$) it was accepted. The occupational status of the residents of Lucknow city also insignificantly affected ($f = 0.857$, $p = 0.357$) their shopping tactics. Finally, the results obtained from both age ($f = 0.619$, $p = 0.433$) and monthly household income ($f = 0.501$, $p = 0.481$) proved insignificantly dominating.

The testing results from four tier II Indian cities comprising Gurugram, Surat, Nashik and

Madurai unambiguously elucidate that there is no significant difference in the effect of factors affecting online shopping among Indian consumers gender wise, marital status wise, educational status wise, occupational status wise, age wise and monthly household income wise.

Analysis of factors affecting Consumer Satisfaction

H₀₃: There is no significant impact of factors affecting online shopping on consumer satisfaction.

Regression analysis was conducted in order to interpret the extent of dependency of customer satisfaction, on the sub-factors of attitude, perception and motivation respectively. The results are elaborated in Table 10.

Table 10. Regression Analysis Result

			R	R ²	B	T	Sig.
Factors	Attitude	C → CS	0.0827	0.008	- 0.131	- 1.749	0.081
		PQ → CS	0.012	0.000	- 0.016	- 0.246	0.806
		RT → CS	0.038	0.001	- 0.052	- 0.751	0.453
	Motivation	VP → CS	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.016	0.987
		FI → CS	0.188	0.035	- 0.212	- 3.812	0.000
	Perception	SF → CS	0.081	0.007	- 0.098	- 1.626	0.105
		T → CS	0.120	0.015	0.112	2.421	0.016

Source: Primary Data

Note: Regression is significant at 0.05 level; C, Convenience; PQ, Poor Quality; RT, Risk Task; SF, Security Facility; T, Trend; VP, Variety of Product; FI, Family Influence; CS, Customer Satisfaction

H_{03.1}: There is no significant impact of factor affecting convenience on consumer satisfaction.

Convenience was taken as independent variable and customer satisfaction as dependent variable. Variance of 0.8% was explained in satisfaction of customers towards online shopping ($R^2 = 0.008$). A negative relationship with weak strength was found ($\beta = -0.131$, $R = 0.0827$) with $p = 0.081$. So, the null hypothesis is failed to reject. Thus, convenience is negatively linked to consumer satisfaction ($t = -1.749$, $p = 0.081$).

H_{03.2}: There is no significant impact of factor affecting poor quality on consumer satisfaction.

A variance of 0% was explained in consumer satisfaction ($R^2 = 0.000$) when poor quality was taken as independent variable and consumer satisfaction as dependent variable. The relationship was found to be negative ($\beta = -0.016$, $R = 0.012$) but strongly strengthened as $p = 0.806$ which is extremely vital. Thus, the null hypothesis is failed to reject ($t = -0.246$, $p = 0.806$). So, poor quality and consumer satisfaction share a negative relationship.

H_{03.3}: There is no significant impact of factor affecting risk task on consumer satisfaction.

When risk task was taken as independent variable and consumer satisfaction as dependent variable, it can be interpreted that the variance was 0.1% in consumer satisfaction ($R^2 = 0.001$) indicating that the strength of the relationship shared is fairly moderate, $p = 0.453$ coupled with a negative relationship ($\beta = -0.052$, $R = 0.038$). The null hypothesis is rejected ($t = -0.751$, $p = 0.453$).

H_{03.4}: There is no significant impact of factor affecting variety of product on consumer satisfaction.

When variety of product is taken as independent variable and consumer satisfaction as dependent variable, the variance was 0% in terms of consumer satisfaction towards online shopping ($R^2 = 0.000$). There is a positive relationship between variety of product and consumer

satisfaction ($\beta = 0.001$, $R = 0.001$). It should also be noted that as p is 0.987 which is greater than 0.05 by an impactful margin and a strong relationship exists between the aforementioned variables. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected ($t = 0.016$, $p = 0.987$).

H_{03.5}: There is no significant impact of factor affecting family influence on consumer satisfaction.

When family influence is assumed to be independent variable and consumer satisfaction as dependent variable explains a 3.5% variance in satisfaction of consumers ($R^2 = 0.035$). A negative relationship is identifiable as β is -0.212 and R is 0.188 elucidating p as 0.000 which has weakened the relationship's strength. This has resulted in the rejection of the null hypothesis expressing that there is no significant impact of factor affecting family influence on consumer satisfaction ($t = -3.812$, $p = 0.000$).

H_{03.6}: There is no significant impact of factor affecting security facility on consumer satisfaction.

A variance of 0.7% was explained in consumer satisfaction ($R^2 = 0.007$) when security facility was taken as independent variable also taking consumer satisfaction as dependent variable. As the value of β equals -0.098 and that of R is 0.081, a negative relationship with moderate strength exists. The value of p being 0.105 justifies the hypothesis thus accepting it. Security facility negatively impacts consumer satisfaction.

H_{03.7}: There is no significant impact of factor affecting trend on consumer satisfaction.

A variance of 1.5% was explained in consumer satisfaction ($R^2 = 0.015$). The analysis resulted in a positive relationship ($\beta = 0.112$, $R = 0.120$) having weak strength with $p = 0.016$. The hypothesis is rejected as $p = 0.016$ which is less when compared to 0.05. Ultimately, trend affects consumer satisfaction.

Discussion

Online shopping has fascinated a lot of consumers due to its advantages and capability to be always readily available (Deshmukh & Joseph, 2016). However, the underlying parameters of online shopping on cross-cultural design need to be constantly assessed for commercial progress. Besides, the dependency of consumer satisfaction on certain factors necessitates the need for objectively scrutinizing the impacting aspects of online shopping experience. This study concentrates on vital aspects so that the tendencies behind a cross-cultural shift in online consumer buying behaviour can be understood.

The respondents belonged to four tier II cities in India - Gurugram, Surat, Nashik and Madurai. The results obtained from Gurugram and Surat deduced none of the factors affect awareness level among consumers. This might indicate the instinctive tendency among online consumers to carefully analyse the product or service attributes before opting for online purchase and attempting to seek redressal directly from e-tailers (Ha & Coghill, 2007). Outcomes from the cities of Madurai and Nashik were slightly different as age seemed to affect the awareness level of online consumers. Perhaps, this is because of the intensified use of internet services among the technologically friendly generation (Hansen et al., 2018). This is quite striking in present times, reinstating the significance of age as an important factor affecting cross-cultural buying behaviour serving as vital parameter for marketers to concentrate on.

After testing the factors associated with consumer satisfaction, it was revealed that none of them succeed in foregoing the insignificant effect of factors affecting online shopping among the consumers of any of the four cities. This indicates a vital blow to the customary buying patterns for satisfaction among online consumers. The impact of family influence seems to hold parallelism with the fact that existence of responsiveness among online business contributors and intentions of repurchase turn out to be dominating determinants that promote satisfaction among

online consumers (Pham & Ahammad, 2017) basically indicating the constant transformation of online shopping in the present times. Resultantly, this has aided in promoting consumer rationality that has impacted their online buying decisions (Ozen & Engizek, 2013).

As variety of products contributes in promoting consumer satisfaction, technical effects of products and services search coupled with identification of web data movement (Hepp, 2009) may lead to a better understanding of consumer mindset. Additionally, trend also enhances the levels of consumer satisfaction owing to expansive product availability on several online platforms (Mishra & Chopra, 2014). As trend is the most sought-after factor, marketing strategies need attention in this regard. Moreover, the strong relationship of security facility with consumer satisfaction denotes heightened secure checkouts (Robinson & Surya, 2019). It should also be mentioned that convenience and risk task averse their satisfaction levels, thereby weakening their relationships, perhaps due to increasingly cautious consumers toward online transactions.

Conclusion

As an individual's life patterns change, his needs also undergo transformation. With the penetration of virtual shops in the lifestyles of Indian consumers, it is important for key stakeholders to understand how online consumer behavior varies in a cross-cultural set-up. Assorted appeal to categorized age-groups belonging to varied workspaces seems to be necessary for a profitable boost in e-business. Online marketers also need to keep the buying patterns in mind and try to earnestly satisfy consumers whenever possible. With constant rise in competition, family influence and trend need to be critically assessed as they promote satisfaction among online consumers belonging to diverse cultural backgrounds. Since there is a paradigm shift in all aspects of life especially post COVID-19, online shopping will empower consumers, enabling them to ensure health and safety along with risk aversion. To sum up, in view of the discussion and suggestions of both

the studies, the researchers are looking forward to witness a highly positive impact of this study on consumers, society and nation as a whole.

Limitations and Future Scope

There are many factors affecting online shopping behavior of consumers and these factors play a prominent role in their buying decisions. But because of time constraints, the researcher did not examine all the factors. This study aims to examine consumer's behavior towards online shopping and thereby consumer satisfaction levels are dependent on the former without specification of any service or product category. Due to time and cost constraints, the researcher examined factors affecting online shopping behavior of online buyers belonging to four tier II culturally diverse cities of India that are more urbanized as compared to others. However, the insights obtained might benefit prospective researchers and scholars to get a new direction in the wide market of online shopping thereby aiding them to explore the behavior of consumers towards online shopping and understand their psychology on a greater level in order to develop new contributions in the field of research.

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